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1  """
2  Tests pour le Président V1.3
3  """
4
5  import pytest
6  from president_v1_3 import PresidentArbitrage, ExpertOutput, AgentType, Decision
7
8  def test_choquet_monotonicity():
9      """Teste que Choquet respecte la monotonie"""
10     president = PresidentArbitrage()
11
12     # Tous les scores augmentent => décision doit augmenter
13     outputs1 = {
14         AgentType.FINANCE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.FINANCE, 0.5, "AUTO", 0.7),
15         AgentType.JURIDIQUE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.JURIDIQUE, 0.5, "AUTO", 0.7),
16         AgentType.SECURITE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.SECURITE, 0.5, "AUTO", 0.7),
17         AgentType.TECHNIQUE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.TECHNIQUE, 0.5, "AUTO", 0.7),
18     }
19
20     outputs2 = {
21         AgentType.FINANCE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.FINANCE, 0.6, "AUTO", 0.7),
22         AgentType.JURIDIQUE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.JURIDIQUE, 0.6, "AUTO", 0.7),
23         AgentType.SECURITE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.SECURITE, 0.6, "AUTO", 0.7),
24         AgentType.TECHNIQUE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.TECHNIQUE, 0.6, "AUTO", 0.7),
25     }
26
27     score1 = president._compute_choquet_integral(outputs1)
28     score2 = president._compute_choquet_integral(outputs2)
29
30     assert score2 >= score1, "Choquet doit être monotone"
31
32 def test_veto_juridique():
33     """Teste le veto juridique"""
34     president = PresidentArbitrage()
35
36     outputs = {
37         AgentType.FINANCE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.FINANCE, 0.95, "APPROUVER", 0.9),
38         AgentType.JURIDIQUE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.JURIDIQUE, 0.15, "REFUSER", 0.9),
39         AgentType.SECURITE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.SECURITE, 0.85, "APPROUVER", 0.9),
40         AgentType.TECHNIQUE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.TECHNIQUE, 0.80, "APPROUVER", 0.8
41     ),
42     }
43
44     artifact = president.arbitrer(outputs)
45     assert artifact.final_decision == Decision.VETO
46     assert any("juridique" in trigger.lower() for trigger in artifact.
47         guardrail_triggers)
48
49 def test_approval_threshold():
50     """Teste le seuil d'approbation"""
51     president = PresidentArbitrage()
52
53     outputs = {
54         AgentType.FINANCE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.FINANCE, 0.85, "APPROUVER", 0.9),
55         AgentType.JURIDIQUE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.JURIDIQUE, 0.75, "APPROUVER", 0.8
56     ),
57         AgentType.SECURITE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.SECURITE, 0.90, "APPROUVER", 0.95),
58         AgentType.TECHNIQUE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.TECHNIQUE, 0.70, "APPROUVER", 0.8
59     ),
60     }
61
62     artifact = president.arbitrer(outputs)
63     assert artifact.final_decision == Decision.APPROUVER
64     assert artifact.choquet_score >= president.config.Guardrails.APPROVAL_THRESHOLD
65
66 def test_governance_hash_integrity():
67     """Teste l'intégrité du hash de gouvernance"""
68     president = PresidentArbitrage()
69
70     outputs = {
71         AgentType.FINANCE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.FINANCE, 0.8, "APPROUVER", 0.9),
72         AgentType.JURIDIQUE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.JURIDIQUE, 0.7, "APPROUVER", 0.8),

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69         AgentType.SECURITE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.SECURITE, 0.9, "APPROUVER", 0.95),
70         AgentType.TECHNIQUE: ExpertOutput(AgentType.TECHNIQUE, 0.6, "APPROUVER", 0.7),
71     }
72
73     artifact = president.arbitrer(outputs)
74
75     # Le hash doit être cohérent
76     assert artifact.governance_hash
77     assert len(artifact.governance_hash) == 16
78
79     # Vérification que le hash correspond au contenu
80     # (simplifiée pour l'exemple)
81     assert artifact.governance_hash == president._compute_governance_hash(artifact)
82
83 if __name__ == "__main__":
84     pytest.main([__file__, "-v"])
```